

Collaborative Information Gathering: A Program of Research

Uwe Borghoff, Natalie Glance, Antonietta Grasso, Jutta Willamowski

Rank Xerox Research Centre, Grenoble Laboratory
6, chemin de Maupertuis. F-38240 Meylan, France
E-mail: <lastname>@grenoble.rxrc.xerox.com

Background and Scenario

Information retrieval technology is commonly positioned as push or pull, where push is the passive receiving of information and pull is the active search of it. We propose in this plan that the two are complementary and fit well into a community-centered scenario. This already happens in our everyday working life: either we need some particular information and actively look for it - most of the time on the basis of suggestion from people we know to be an expert of the field - or we receive information from the environment - mostly from social and working interactions.

The *Constraint-Based Knowledge Broker* (CBKB) environment [ABP⁺95, ABP96] is typical of pull technologies: it provides a uniform interface to search engines [BoSc96, CBC97], asynchronously searched by issuing queries [BCW96]. In the current implementation the system does not provide any facility either to involve other people in the definition of the query, to evaluate the results, or to publish them (beside basic functionality to export them in HTML format).

The *Knowledge Pump*TM [GPA⁺97] is typical of push technologies: it provides a community shared environment supporting the (asynchronous as well as synchronous) flow and use of knowledge among the community members on the basis of their interactions and recommendations.

The activity of searching is one step of a more complex social process (see Figure1):

- each information search is not a stand-alone entity, but is part of a permanent chain where advice about *where*, *what* and *how* to search comes from other people [COT⁺97];
- information searches are shared among people by updating team membership, consulting, communicating and putting the results in shared archives.

Fig. 1: - Life cycle of information searches

In particular, the outcomes of the case study reported in [DaJe93a, DaJe93b] are relevant and provide some insight about how information search processes are shared. Four basic models have been identified:

1. sharing results with other members of a team.
2. self-initiated broadcast of interesting information encountered in search results: this pattern is used when unexpected but interesting tidbits are encountered and circulated to people across the organization expected to find them useful. Very often the relevant information is extracted before passing it along. This pattern implies understanding the profiles of the people as well elaborating a proper format for circulating it (e.g. a spreadsheet with financial information). This pattern results in a member of several communities publishing and distributing information when appropriate.

3. acting as a consultant, handling repeated or ad hoc information search requests made by others. Communities ask a member with the proper profile to act as a consultant.
4. archiving potentially useful information into a group repository.

An interesting point raised in the case study is that only in a few situations the results were not shared in any way.

In our research plan, we assume that CBKB, with extensions coming from Knowledge Pump, can be made useful as a cooperative tool provided that it is integrated in a community oriented environment in such a way that the queries and results become permanent shared resources (see Figure 2).

Synchronous collaboration	Asynchronous collaboration
Consultation of experts	Awareness about community activities
Distributed allocation of expertise	Voluntary advice
	From tacit to explicit knowledge

Fig. 2: Different types of collaboration

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